

SCENARIOS FOR THE INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL EXCHANGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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About FRAMES

FRAMES “Fostering resilience through Accredited Mobility for European Sustainable Higher Education innovation” aims to foster an harmonised implementation and accreditation of Virtual Exchange, as an integral part of (blended) mobility approaches, among European Higher Education Institutions, making the European Higher Education Area more innovative, intercultural and resilient.

The project is funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union and spans over 2 years (March 2021 – February 2023).

FRAMES is implemented by:

UNIMED – Mediterranean Universities Union (Italy)

UNICollaboration (Spain)

Sharing Perspective (The Netherlands)

University of Girona (Spain)

University of Limerick (Ireland)

University of Siena (Italy)

More information on the Project can be found at: <https://frames-project.eu/>

Partners

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RATIONALE FOR THIS STUDY AND METHODOLOGY

01

— INTRODUCTION

This report is aimed at teaching and administrative staff interested in implementing Virtual Exchange (VE) as part of broader mobility/internationalisation strategies within their universities, and who would hence like to know more about how to integrate and accredit it in practice. Evidence shows that motivation is crucial for the success of any educational intervention, including VEs, and that accreditation plays an important role in increasing participants' motivation and commitment. While research has mainly focused on describing VE as an educational practice, this report aims at showing, through selected cases, how VE has been integrated and accredited by Higher Education Institutions. The cases are used to illustrate four different scenarios of integration and accreditation of VE, including challenges and opportunities, and help the reader identify potential paths for future implementation of this innovative pedagogy within their institutions.

— ABOUT FRAMES

This report represents the first Intellectual Output of FRAMES, a Strategic Partnership funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union spanning over 2 years (March 2021 – February 2023). The project is implemented by a consortium composed of UNIMED – Mediterranean Universities Union (coordinator), UNICollaboration, Sharing Perspectives Foundation, University of Girona, University of Limerick, and University of Siena.

FRAMES aims to foster a harmonised implementation and accreditation of Virtual Exchange, as an integral part of (blended) mobility approaches, among European Higher Education Institutions (HEI), making the European Higher Education Area more innovative, intercultural and resilient.

VE as an educational practice has been shown to work as a complementary component of physical exchange programmes, allowing more students to benefit from meaningful international and intercultural experiences as part of their higher education. Now it is time for EU universities to mainstream this approach into their institutionalised mobility activities.

To facilitate this, the project will:

- valorise successful scenarios of accredited VE, showing them to be an innovative, inclusive and intercultural complement to physical mobility;
- build the capacity of European HEIs to integrate and accredit VE as a key component of their mobility activities;
- support HEIs, European Universities and HEI Networks in creating the conditions for a long-term harmonised integration and accreditation of physical, blended and virtual mobility.

METHODOLOGY

In order to identify and describe the various scenarios of accredited VEs, the consortium decided to collect and analyse existing VE case studies from multiple sources. The primary sources used were the EVOLVE¹ report and a published collection of case studies², due to the fact that they represent the most in-depth and updated collections of VE Case Studies relevant for the purposes of this study.

The consortium partners were also invited to map relevant initiatives from their or other institutions to be considered for inclusion in the collection of case studies. In addition, a survey was sent out to potential stakeholders in order to collect further examples.

By using a pattern analysis methodology (so as to extract from different experiences similar patterns that can be applied to every European HEI), the project team aggregated the collected cases into scenarios that could potentially be used by a variety of European Higher Education Institutions.

71 cases were mapped and 12 selected to be included in this report. The final selection of the 12 case studies described in this report was done collaboratively by the partners. The criteria for the selection of cases were:

- Specific criteria within scenarios: extent to which the initiative illustrates at least one scenario; “high impact”; quality over quantity, potential for transferability to other HEIs in Europe; sustainability in the short and long term; permanent addition to the curriculum, rather than the VE being seen as an ad hoc measure aimed at replacing physical mobility in an emergency situation (COVID-19); overarching integration / accreditation strategy in place or in progress; potential for scalability while maintaining quality & sustainability;
- General criteria: geographical spread; interdisciplinarity; different types of institutions.

QUALITY ASSURANCE MECHANISM

Each partner was asked to complete one or more detailed case studies on a mapped initiative comprising 71 cases as a whole, using a common template. Each of the case studies was reviewed by a different partner institution. All partners reviewed the concepts behind the various scenarios, and were invited to review the drafts of the report. An external review was conducted by Anna Turula, the external quality expert appointed for the project.

¹https://pure.rug.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/151946440/EVOLVE_Case_Studies_Report_Final_201223.pdf

²<https://research-publishing.net/publication/978-2-490057-72-6.pdf>

— CASE STUDIES INCLUDED

- e-Tandem Project
- i-TELL PREP
- Trans-Atlantic Engagement
- Euroweek
- NICE project
- Soliya Connect Program
- Climate Movements
- Teaching and Learning in Primary Education in International Comparison
- Shared Garden
- University of Applied Sciences, Utrecht
- Julius Maximilian University (JMU), Würzburg
- Communication across cultures

AN OVERVIEW OF VIRTUAL EXCHANGE AND DEFINITIONS

02

Study abroad and other forms of physical mobility have been an important component of the educational offerings of HEIs in many areas of the world in the last decades, and since 1987 the Erasmus programme in Europe has enabled millions of students to obtain an international experience as part of their university education. International mobility has been shown to “improve students’ employability and the development of transversal skills such as interpersonal and intercultural skills and competences, self-confidence, the ability to achieve goals and social and cultural openness [...], exposing students to new career fields and possibilities as well as global connections [... and can help] develop skills that foster social cohesion, such as learning to get along better with people from different cultures and taking a stand against discrimination or intolerance (Helm et al, 2020)³.

Nevertheless, there are significant barriers to physical mobility, the most frequent being financial, family, health and employment reasons. This means that over 9 out of 10 students do not take part in a physical mobility programme. Therefore, there is little diversity in the group of students who do go abroad: having a higher socioeconomic background, they are often the ones who have greater travel experience, while the more disadvantaged students may be missing out on an international component to their university education.

In recent years, stakeholders have been looking into Virtual Exchange (VE), which can complement existing forms of physical mobility, as a more inclusive way to obtain an international and intercultural experience. Research has found that VE can help develop students’ intercultural and communicative skills, digital literacies, intergroup relations and their ability to work in international teams⁴. Virtual exchange can also contribute to the internationalisation of the curriculum and Internationalisation at Home (IaH) initiatives.

There are two basic forms of VE that can be integrated into higher-education curricula. The first is what can be termed “ready-made” programmes, where pedagogical experts from external educational providers (see Soliya⁵ or Sharing Perspectives Foundation⁶) have developed virtual exchange projects based on facilitated dialogue. The core component of these programmes is thus synchronous dialogue led by facilitators. During weekly ‘live’ sessions, the students meet in small groups to discuss different topics – often around global issues – with peers from a variety of geographical and cultural backgrounds, with the help of trained dialogue facilitators. The second model of VE is the teacher-designed project, in which educators in HEIs develop a project with one or more partners in a different country to integrate a more international and intercultural perspective into their courses, thus maintaining full control over the contents and duration of the programme.

³https://www.handbook-internationalisation.com/media/02818d033e0d8e74995aed9e16e1bb8970060360/r7aklh/pdf_5e81ffb452439.pdf

⁴Ibid

⁵<https://soliya.net/>

⁶<https://sharingperspectivesfoundation.com/>

The VE can be developed in any discipline and subject area, or can be transdisciplinary. This enables the students and teachers to acquire different perspectives on their subject while learning to collaborate with their international peers through the use of ICT.

Although the field of VE is not new, there is still some confusion in the terminology used by different stakeholders, particularly when referring to virtual mobility and exchange, blended mobility or MOOCs. While ICT is at the centre of all these educational practices, there are significant differences. Within the FRAMES project, we differentiate these concepts as follows:

Virtual Exchange: The Virtual Exchange Coalition defines VE as “technology-enabled, sustained, people-to-people education programs”⁷. In other words, there is an element of collaboration and exchange between participants, with a focus not only on content learning, but also on the development of transversal skills, including intercultural communication and digital literacies. A core principle is that the collaboration needs to be sustained: in other words, a one-off meeting – such as taking part in a webinar – does not constitute a VE project. Terms such as COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning⁸), Global Digital Exchange, Telecollaboration, Teletandem and e-Tandem (the latter three used primarily in the area of foreign language learning) all share the same defining elements.

Virtual Mobility: we define Virtual Mobility here as educational practices that allow students from one educational institution to follow courses organised at a different institution (usually based in a different country) without having to leave home. The essential component of VE, which is the intercultural learning obtained through collaboration between students in the two institutions, is not necessary here: the focus of Virtual Mobility is to provide subject knowledge (possibly in an area or a specific topic not taught at the student’s home university) by taking advantage of complementary expertise, and does not require the student to interact with peers from the host institution.

Blended Mobility can be defined as “a combination of physical mobility with a virtual component facilitating a collaborative online learning exchange and teamwork. For example, the virtual component can bring learners together online from different countries and study fields to follow online courses or work collectively and simultaneously on assignments that are recognised as part of their studies⁹.” A blended mobility can therefore integrate a physical mobility period with a Virtual Exchange project (see Helm & O’Dowd’s 2019 position paper¹⁰).

⁷<http://virtualexchangecoalition.org/>

⁸<https://online.suny.edu/introtocoil/suny-coil-what-is/>

⁹<https://erasmusplus.eupa.org/mt/higher-education-funding/>

¹⁰<https://www.unicollaboration.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Position-paper-on-Blended-Mobility.pdf>

MOOCs: Massive Open Online Courses are courses usually delivered online through a platform such as EdX, Coursera or Futurelearn. The focus of these is primarily on content delivery – they are mostly based on recorded video lectures and learning materials. Although many have a forum component and encourage students to interact, the interaction is not sustained and is optional.

iOOCs: Interactive Open Online Courses, such as the ones offered by the Sharing Perspectives Foundation, combine content presented in a similar format to MOOCs, with an interactive component which includes weekly synchronous discussion sessions in small groups with the support of a dialogue facilitator, to encourage people-to-people intercultural communication.

There are two further terms we need to define in the context of the FRAMES project. Although **recognition** and **accreditation** have different meanings in different contexts, here we use the word **recognition** to refer to the process of granting official status to the knowledge, skills and competences developed as a result of a course or of an educational experience (e.g. an internship) by an HEI. This can be done, for example, through the award of certificates, open badges or credits. If the process of recognition involves the granting of credits, then we refer to accreditation of the learning process.

SCENARIOS FOR THE INTEGRATION OF VE PROJECTS

03

In the following section, we briefly outline the different scenarios in which VE projects can be integrated into the curriculum. The cases we provide are concrete illustrative examples of VEs carried out in various HEIs, and should help the reader get a better idea of how the scenarios can take shape.

3.1. VIRTUAL EXCHANGE AS A PREPARATORY OR FOLLOW-UP ACTIVITY TO PHYSICAL MOBILITY (BLENDED MOBILITY)

Using VE as a preparatory or follow-up activity to physical mobility means that the VE is offered to students either before or after the physical mobility exchange. In this sense, such a scenario is an example of blended mobility.

The aims and benefits of the VE vary according to when it takes place. If the VE is offered before the physical exchange, it mainly aims to prepare students linguistically, culturally, but also psychologically, for the period they will spend abroad. When the VE takes place after the international exchange, it is mainly aimed at reinforcing the experience by allowing students to reflect on their learning together with their international peers and foster cooperation after mobility. In some cases, the VE can take place after the physical exchange of one cohort and before the exchange of a different cohort from the same institution: in this specific case, when both former and future mobile students from the same institution are involved, the VE also enables these two groups to bond socially, building upon the experience of the former to prepare the latter for the exchange.

Three successful examples of VE being used as a pre-departure or post-return offering are the e-Tandem offered by the University of Padova, the i-Tell project involving the Universities of Limerick and León, and the Trans-Atlantic Engagement, an educational initiative organised by the University of Newcastle and Indiana University.

— E-TANDEM

Developed by the Language Centre of the University of Padova in collaboration with the International Office (IO) in 2015, eTandem is a VE project between incoming international students and domestic students interested in a language and intercultural exchange. It runs twice a year for 8 to 10 weeks before each semester starts. All domestic students, in particular future outgoing ones, as well as international students planning to study at the University of Padova in the following semester(s) are invited to apply.

A substantial number of the domestic students are enrolled in languages and literature degree courses. Another substantial group are future 'outgoing' students interested in practising their language and/or learning more about the country and university system where they will be studying.

The most recent edition involved 65 Italian and 150 international students from all over the world.

The students are put in contact through the multilingual e-community, where discussion topics are suggested by the moderators, and mixed groups of eight to 12 students take part in regular facilitated dialogue sessions; the students are also paired for their tandem sessions, when speaking time is equally split between Italian and the other target languages, for both students to benefit from the language exchange. Students are matched according to different criteria: their destination/country of origin, study area, and language chosen.

Weekly self-reflection diaries are compiled by students on the learning platform, to enable them to think about the intercultural issues addressed in the e-community. This 'writing space' also helps tutors to monitor the project development, in particular the constant interaction between students in their one-to-one interactions, and to adjust the project to students' needs, competences, and suggestions. A final reflection paper and feedback questionnaires are also required at the end of the project.

The aims of the project are therefore:

1. Linguistic: it enables students to practice their target language(s) in the one-to-one exchange, and the various *linguae francae* in the online multilingual and multicultural community.
2. Cultural and intercultural: students' cultural and intercultural awareness is gradually fostered, by enhancing their curiosity towards others, familiarising them with different cultures and deepening their knowledge of their own culture.
3. Social: the project helps international students integrate with those of the host country.
4. Technological and digital: students are encouraged to learn how to behave responsibly online, by experiencing opportunities and potential risks linked to social networks.

Domestic students enrolled in language and literature degree courses are awarded 3 ECTS credits upon successful completion of the project, formalised as an optional activity within their curriculum, while other participants are not awarded credits, as they take part on a voluntary basis. All students are nevertheless issued a certificate of attendance when they successfully complete the required activities.

— I-TELL PREP

The i-TELL PREP (Intercultural Telecollaborative Learning for Pre-mobility preparation) project, initiated in September 2014, aimed to respond to the need to increase students' intercultural awareness before their mobility period while improving their linguistic, cultural and digital competences. In addition, it intended to explore the impact that this pre-departure intervention had on students.

The students involved were undergraduates from a variety of disciplines, studying Spanish or English as part of their degree courses. Eight students of Spanish from the University of Limerick in Ireland were paired with eight students of English from the University of León in Spain. All participants were set to go respectively to Spain for a study or work placement, and to the UK or Ireland for study. A task-based approach was chosen as the most appropriate. During an eight-week period, students had to complete collaborative tasks on cultural and intercultural topics such as the home university, the host country, expectations about living abroad, and comparing university life and academic systems in the two countries. The VE was carried out using email, video recordings and video conferencing tools. Throughout the duration of the project, the students had weekly face-to-face meetings in small groups of around 10 students with the project facilitator, and they were advised to have two weekly exchanges with their international peers. Each exchange was conducted half in Spanish and half in English.

In terms of participation, the Irish students took part in the project on a voluntary basis, receiving a certificate of participation at completion, whereas the Spanish students received 2 ECTS credits. After the first iteration, the project has evolved and has brought together different initiatives under the umbrella of the Ready, Mobility, Go! programme.

— TRANS-ATLANTIC ENGAGEMENT

An educational exchange was developed in 2015 between Newcastle University School of Dental Sciences (NUSDS) and Indiana University School of Dentistry in the United States of America (IUSD), enabling students to learn alongside each other within dental and community settings in both countries, which have significantly different healthcare systems. For each cohort of UK and US students, the exchange is spanned over 2 academic years: in the first academic year, a VE takes place from January to May as initial preparation to the physical exchange, before the US students visit the UK for 10 days (May/June); in the second academic year, the VE takes place from May to July, and then UK students visit the USA for 2 weeks in July.

The exchange aims to allow students to gain mutual awareness of delivery, access to care and possible barriers facing patients relating to the oral healthcare systems in England, the State of Indiana and the USA in general.

The programme is now in its fourth cycle. Students participate in a unique face-to-face collaborative and interdisciplinary education programme within respective dental schools and community settings. The students' physical exchange is supported by a series of videoconferences/webinars scheduled before the on-site visits. These videoconferences allow for elements of the programme to be formally co-taught by staff from NUSDS and IUSD in preparation for the short physical exchange abroad, and enable staff and students to get to know one another before meeting face-to-face. Students then undertake their own informal peer exchange through their choice of social media platform.

To enable such an exchange, close collaboration between dental academics and students, alongside support from their respective universities, was imperative. For staff closely involved with the programme, the opportunity for collaborative curriculum development and educational research were also important goals. Reciprocal visiting lectureships were awarded to the educators by their hosting university, facilitating collaboration between them.

During the reciprocal visits to the partner dental schools, students were fully registered within the host university, immersing themselves in being dental students within that establishment as much as possible. To align the ages of each cohort as closely as possible, 1st year US students and 3rd year UK students were recruited, after a competitive call for application. It was important to recruit students within the first Semester/Term of the new academic year in order to optimise both the communication between the students and their attendance at future educational videoconferences. Careful scheduling of the physical exchanges avoided examinations or other curricular clashes.

Prior to the exchange, several live, one-hour videoconferencing (webinar) sessions were organised to facilitate student orientation, introductions and wider student learning related to health policy, local demographics and comparison of the oral health between the UK and US. The first was a 'get to know you' session with staff present only at the start and end as facilitators. The remainder encompassed joint discussions based upon an open access journal publication comparing UK and US oral health surveys, an introduction to a senior Oral Health Educator based in Newcastle community clinics, discussion of the types of clinical and non-clinical experiences the students would value, and initial induction into the dental hospitals/schools and student life in the UK and the US. To further prepare IUSD students to deliver Oral Health Education (OHE) within community settings, they were given access to a recording of the OHE induction lecture given in Newcastle as part of the School's dental outreach course. OHE to a range of community groups is a compulsory part of the career of dental students at both institutions.

All participating staff and students were enrolled onto the IU course networking platform which provided a closed group to aid sharing of information, and a discussion forum outside of timetabled videoconferences. The students (independently) formed a closed group within a separate social media platform.

After the exchange, Newcastle students were required to provide an Elective Report to the Head of School which included key areas of reflection upon personal learning outcomes, while IUSD students were required to complete a reflective journal based upon personal learning goals and observations. Additionally, to further develop visits to NUSDS by IUSD students, they were invited to complete reflective clinical logs during each clinical session or OHE visit. These helped future timetabling in the UK. All students and key staff were involved in a series of focus groups. Students from both sides of the Atlantic have presented reflections and experiences verbally and via posters at university or national level and have been key players in recruiting the next cohorts of potential exchange students.

The physical exchange and the intertwined VE were part of an array of elective studies available, which students joined in pre-COVID-19 times to expand their general and cultural knowledge and skills. Thus, the programme does not count towards the degree and students join on a purely voluntary basis. The main incentive for students to take part is that they can include this experience in their CVs and professional portfolios.

With the COVID-19 outbreak, the availability of virtual/online communication applications such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams increased and training was provided rapidly. As the physical exchange was temporarily suspended, an opportunity was seized for further development of the NUSDS elective programme along a virtual route. Counterparts in Indiana, Indonesia and Fiji were contacted resulting in the co-development of a wholly 'virtual elective' pilot lasting 4 weeks. Indiana were unable to commit due to pandemic pressures, however volunteer undergraduates from NUSDS, University of Indonesia Dental School and University of Fiji Dental School formed diverse small groups tasked with working together on a self-chosen dental project, using their preferred method(s) of virtual communication tools. Students were advised to have a minimum of 4 group video meetings over that period and encouraged to keep in contact in between. A welcome meeting was hosted on the Saturday before the exchange started. Their projects culminated in virtual group presentations to various university staff and their peers during a final meeting; the overall winner was a hard-hitting film made by 3 students on how COVID-19 had affected them as dental students in different parts of the world. Students wrote a reflective journal/log throughout their virtual communications, highlighting challenges and successes. These reflections were submitted to the electives lead in NUSDS to aid quality assurance and further evolution of the programme.

— OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

These three projects have been shown to have a great impact on students' preparation for their mobility experience. The first two provided students with guidance and support on the practical and logistic aspects of living abroad: as well as being able to practise their target languages, students became aware of academic matters such as the university systems, timetables, facilities, class sizes, student life and aspects of daily life such as accommodation, prices and eating habits.

In the case of the Trans-Atlantic Engagement in dental education, the VE also provided students with subject knowledge, such as health policies, local demographics and comparison between oral healthcare practices in the UK and the US. The time and effort put in by all participants during the VE phase prior to the physical exchange was reflected in the way the students greeted each other when they finally met face-to-face; friendships were already forged. It was also beneficial to build-in some face-to-face social events during the weekend before the 'working weeks' of the physical exchange, because these activities enhanced inter-group collaboration. Furthermore, staff involved in Indiana work were invited to a virtual celebration of the broader "uni to uni collaboration" and the students did a lot of socialising throughout via their closed FB group.

In addition, both the eTandem and the I-Tell projects show that it is possible not only to involve all future (and past) mobile students, but also students who may be interested in an online exchange to practise their target language and develop intercultural skills and knowledge about different educational contexts. These students can then become "buddies" of incoming students, obtaining an international experience at home.

In a pre-departure VE such as the e-Tandem project, a main challenge can arise from the wide variety of students who take part in the VE activities: coming from different countries, the students often have different levels of language proficiency and/or subject-matter knowledge, as well as varying levels of maturity (particularly if the project includes both undergraduate and postgraduate students). Overcoming initial potential misunderstandings and making students leave their comfort zone may hence take longer or be more difficult than for other VE scenarios.

Another challenge is that the VE activity may be accredited and recognised only in specific circumstances or within a given degree course, but not for all students, unless it has been fully integrated at institutional level as propaedeutic to the physical mobility, for example by inserting the VE within already existing "mobility preparation" or "transversal skills" modules.

In the case of the Trans-Atlantic Engagement, neither the preparatory VE nor the physical exchange itself are accredited, and the only motivator for students is the possibility of including the experience in their CVs. Considering the profile of students, the discipline they are studying and the undeniable benefits from participating in the programme for their future profession, motivation of participants is quite high, yet further improving the project by having it accredited as is done would further enhance students' motivation and would enable students to receive evidence of the international experience they did during their university career. Hence, it is highly recommended that the various units concerned with credit recognition are involved in the design and implementation process from its very beginning and work closely with the units responsible for mobility programmes as well as with programme coordinators, to ensure that this type of VE is fully recognised for all participating students.

An additional challenge could arise when the VE, organised as a preparatory activity by one HEI (as in the e-Tandem project), is offered to all its future incoming and outgoing students: unless the home universities of the incoming students are directly involved, the students from those institutions may feel less committed to the VE, and may consequently drop out half way through the programme. It is therefore important that these students' home universities understand the benefit that the VE offers their own students, and take on the responsibility of ensuring commitment on the part of their students. The development of this kind of initiative within University Alliances can be a way to ensure commitment on the part of all the parties involved (see also the NICE project in the next section).

At the same time, it can be advantageous to have a lead university, particularly during the pilot phase, especially when the VE project is multilateral (as is the case in the current evolution of the Trans-Atlantic engagement, which has expanded to include Indonesia and Fiji, where organisation and communication were aided greatly by local administrative support provided by NUSDS and a shared Microsoft Team's Group based within NU).

Future sustainability of such initiatives, where the VE is combined with a physical exchange, may also be a challenge unless funding is secured for the physical exchange. In Europe, financial support for short-term mobility may come from the Erasmus+ programme, or from the European University Alliances funding budget. From the perspective of returning to the in-person exchange in the UK-USA educational initiative, NUSDS is exploring enhancing the University's goal of 'Widening Participation' by pursuing recurrent bursary-type funding awards to ensure access to this international exchange conforms to the School's ethos related to equality, diversity and inclusion. The virtual elective pilot was a great success and will continue beyond the pandemic as another type of more inclusive elective experience.

3.2. VIRTUAL EXCHANGE AS AN INTERTWINED COMPONENT OF PHYSICAL MOBILITY (BLENDED MOBILITY)

A Virtual Exchange as an intertwined component of physical mobility is another example of blended mobility. In this case, the VE is “intertwined” with physical mobility into a single educational experience from its design phase.

The VE may take place while students are abroad, for example through a “while abroad” module designed by two or more institutions. It may also take place as part of a specific initiative, like a summer school, an international conference or workshop, or a broader initiative, for example for students to set up a specific project during their mobility. This means that the VE does not necessarily have to take place while the students are abroad. However, the VE should be directly related to the activities undertaken during the physical mobility period.

Examples of successful VE activities as intertwined components of a physical mobility are the **Euroweek** and the **Network for Intercultural Competence to facilitate Entrepreneurship (NICE)**¹¹. Both of these cases show how VE activities are designed in direct connection to the activities that take place during the physical mobility period. The specific tasks and activities completed virtually, which often include subject-related content, are crucial for the students to be able to participate in the activities undertaken during the physical mobility period.

— EUROWEEK

Euroweek is an annual event, organised by Prime Networking¹², a European network of 17 universities. The aim of this network is to develop and advance cross-cultural and interdisciplinary training, academic programmes and research in the fields of business and economics in a manner which is responsive to a changing global environment. Its main event is a one-week academic conference bringing together students and academics from member universities. Students from two or three different institutions cooperate to develop a project online during the months before the Euroweek event. Then, during the conference week, the student teams present the results of their research projects, attend other workshops and compete for prizes. This initiative is open to both undergraduates and postgraduates, so there is a rich diversity in the level of students.

The VE activities are directly related to the physical mobility element (the Euroweek conference). At the beginning of the academic year, the member universities identify and select the students that will participate in the Euroweek, and teams are composed of students from different universities.

¹¹<https://www.nice-eu.org/>

¹²<https://primenetworking.eu/about-us/>

These teams are given a specific project, on which they will work for 3 months and prepare to communicate their findings during the face-to-face Euroweek event. Students are expected to write a paper, prepare a poster and present the results, in the form of a pitch and a longer presentation. The different student groups are then evaluated and given prizes based on evaluation criteria that take into account academic content, presentation skills and interactive performance with the audience¹³.

The recognition and accreditation of the Euroweek is decentralised and varies for each participating university. For some institutions, Euroweek is offered as an independent course leading to credit recognition of the activities. Other universities recognise it as independent (free) credits, in other words, credits given for elective courses and activities.

Quality is assured through jury evaluations during the annual conference. Juries are created by the host institution, in consultation with the person responsible on the PRIME Managing Board. There are marking grids of project presentations to assure the quality of the evaluation.

While the learning outcomes vary every year depending on the theme of the conference, Euroweek is a clear example of a blended mobility initiative that promotes transversal skills:

- learning to work in multidisciplinary and international teams;
- communicating scientifically in intercultural contexts;
- working under pressure;
- developing leadership skills;
- problem solving;
- developing digital skills.

Both teachers and students recognise that the virtual collaboration component is crucial for the success of this activity. Euroweek has a 3-month-long virtual collaboration component followed by a very intense face to face week. This virtual component sets the foundation for the physical mobility and all the work that the students are expected to do and present. This initiative is particularly interesting because it entails a multidisciplinary teamwork approach with students coming from different disciplinary fields (business, engineering, psychology etc.), and above all provides a meaningful intercultural experience for the participants, students and lecturers alike.

¹³For information on Euroweek 2020, see http://euroweek2020.ihu.gr/docs/EUROWEEK_2020_GUIDELINES.pdf

— NICE PROJECT

The Network for Intercultural Competence to facilitate Entrepreneurship (NICE) is a blended exchange programme, consisting of an introductory course on intercultural competence and entrepreneurship centred around solving a real-world problem, aimed at students from all disciplines and study levels.

For the virtual element, NICE students complete seven online modules, each with a topic related to intercultural competence and entrepreneurship, as they work in mixed teams towards developing a solution to their preferred Global Challenge. Each module requires students to complete individual work in their own time, meet virtually with their team to complete group work, and attend an online session as a team with a dialogue facilitator to discuss progress and milestones and clarify any misunderstandings.

For the physical element, the summer school incorporates interactive sessions with lecturers and entrepreneurs, student group work, team pitches, and a cultural and social programme to foster a sense of community. It is designed to build on the knowledge students acquired from the online programme, as well as provide a chance to apply their newly developed intercultural competences.

For the recognition and accreditation of the NICE activities, a centralised approach has been adopted whereby NICE has developed a mechanism for providing credits to students undertaking a VE programme, through the NICE SLICC ((Student-Led, Individually-Created Course). The NICE SLICC is a self-designed, experiential learning assignment, where students reflect on their experience of working within a transnational team to address a Global Challenge. The course is based on the creation of an e-portfolio, which is a space for students to provide evidence of their learning. As a supplementary and optional component of the NICE programme, the NICE SLICC adds an extra layer of virtual learning. This course requires students to demonstrate the development of their skills and understanding in terms of critical analysis, application, reflection, recognition and development of their skills and mindsets, and evaluation within a defined context of their learning experience. Unlike the online modules, which require group work and interpersonal communication, in the NICE SLICC students are encouraged to reflect on their individual learning goals. Each SLICC student is assigned a tutor who provides feedback on the student's proposal and interim report, and grades their final reflective report.

However, accreditation of the SLICC remains the responsibility of the single university. The University of Edinburgh provides formal accreditation and awards 10 ECTS credits to each individual participant on successful completion of their NICE SLICC¹⁴. Other partners have begun to explore how to incorporate reflective learning within their own institutions.

¹⁴See <https://www.ed.ac.uk/global/go-abroad/nice-programme>

The University of Amsterdam is creating a course that is based on the core concepts of the NICE SLICC and reflective learning. University College Dublin adapted the NICE SLICC to the needs of their own students. At the University of Padova, a General Course on “Intercultural Competence to Facilitate Entrepreneurship” was created, which allows for the accreditation of the NICE project with 6 ECTS.

From 2017 to 2020, EU funding covered the costs of resource development, programme administration, and also student travel and accommodation for the in-person summer school (2019 only). Going forward, there is no financial contribution required from partners to participate in the NICE programme, but each partner must invest a significant amount of staff time and effort. The NICE programme has been continued beyond its EU-funded period with 6 of the original consortium members in 2021, and it was also opened to students from the U21, UNA Europa, EPICUR, and ENLIGHT university alliances. The goal is to open up the network even more widely in 2022 and beyond, by actively seeking new partners to join. Any new partner participating in the programme will join through an existing relationship with one of the original NICE consortium members. The original partner will act as a mentor to the new partner, providing advice on the recruitment, application, and selection process, as well as providing ad hoc support for the facilitators and administrators working on the programme for the first time.

— OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Both of these examples show that VE activities designed to match activities during physical mobility reinforce each other, with the VE activities preparing the ground for the physical component, and deepening and extending the learning. Consequently, they allow universities to create a semester-long international and intercultural experience with only a short physical mobility period. Thus, this type of activity becomes more inclusive of students who are unable to travel for longer periods of time, and diversifies the participating student body.

Both projects report high satisfaction rates among the participants, who see these opportunities as unique learning experiences that suit the current globalised and digitised world of employment. Even for students who do not get this experience accredited at their local institutions, the possibility of including the experience in their CV is already supportive of their future career paths and can increase internship opportunities. That said, it is recognised that the accreditation of the activities is a strong motivator and thereby limits attrition during the project. As these activities rely on collaborative work and thus attrition of students harms other students' experience, efforts should be made to accredit the activities equally across the participating institutions.

However, when it comes to recognition and especially accreditation, HEIs often follow their own procedures, with individual universities often granting credits to their own students as if the VE had been delivered only by the university itself. This sometimes renders the international dimension of the experience invisible. This is an area in which there is space for the member universities to further collaborate in order to find a shared recognition and accreditation process.

Sustainability of these activities heavily depends on the willingness and ability of the participating institutions to invest in the project with staff hours and – in some cases – the hosting of the physical mobility. While external funding has been used in the development and design of the projects mentioned in this section, sustainability beyond the initial funding phases ultimately depends on the participating institutions' investment of resources.

Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic has prevented both projects from holding physical mobility. As a result, the Euroweek conference and the NICE summer school were held online to allow for the continuation of the projects. While those responsible for both initiatives express their intentions to go back to the in-person mobility activities when this can be safely organised, the 2020–21 format does show that the activities can also be successfully organised online in their entirety.

3.3. VIRTUAL EXCHANGE AS A STAND-ALONE LEARNING ACTIVITY

A VE as a stand-alone learning activity means that it is not embedded within a longer module, nor is it seen as a part of a blended educational experience. As such, the VE in itself is recognised as a learning activity and therefore leads to the granting of credits upon completion.

The positioning of this accreditation can be done as part of a broader curriculum, for example by offering the VE as a compulsory or elective course within a languages degree; the VE can also constitute a "practicum", in other words one involving practical work, that sits alongside more theoretical courses. Alternatively, the VE can be offered as part of a pool of "General Key Qualifications" or transversal skills modules offered to students across the different disciplines and courses of study. In this way, the VE can be offered to all students, following an interdisciplinary approach. Finally, the VE can be positioned as an extracurricular activity and listed in a diploma supplement with additional credits, recognising the international and/or intercultural experience of the student in the VE.

Adding a VE as a stand-alone learning activity within the curricula offered supports the institution's Internationalisation at Home (IaH) strategy. It complements other mobility programmes and is specifically suitable for students who, for various reasons, cannot take part in the physical mobility schemes offered by their institution.

Examples of the integration of a VE as a stand-alone learning activity are the Soliya Connect Program offered at the University of Padova since 2009, the Climate Movements programme designed by the Sharing Perspectives Foundation, which is offered at the Engineering School ESIEE Paris, and the "Teaching and Learning in Primary Education in International Comparison", included in the educational offer of the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg. The first 2 examples show how a VE organised by an external institution can be offered as a stand-alone learning activity. This option requires minimal time investment from staff at the university, and allows students to benefit from long-standing VE programmes with a validated ability to foster the development of transversal skills, cross-cultural awareness and empathy. The last case is a class-to-class VE developed at the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg.

— SOLIYA CONNECT PROGRAM

The Soliya Connect Program¹⁵ is a VE established in 2003 by the NGO Soliya, aiming to provide participants with a deeper understanding of the perspectives of others on important socio-political issues and to foster skills such as critical thinking, communication, and digital media literacy.

The involvement of students from the University of Padova (UNIPD) in Soliya's 8-week Connect Programme started in 2009. Since then, every year, between 20 and 50 UNIPD students from two departments – the Department of Linguistic and Literary Studies (DiSLL) and the Department of Political Science, Law, and International Studies (SPGI) – have been taking part in the Programme, the two departments having signed agreements with the organisation.

At SPGI, the 8-week Connect Programme has been offered as an alternative to the Advanced English Language Courses for students of European Studies and Human Rights. The socio-political themes addressed in the VE programme, as well as the skills it fosters, make it an ideal opportunity for students to develop their English language skills in conjunction with other competences, while acquiring the perspectives of young people living in very different geographical areas.

The opportunity to participate in the Connect Programme at DiSLL met the need to provide an engaging opportunity for students to develop confidence in their target language, English.

¹⁵<https://soliya.net/connect-program>

At DiSLL the Connect Program is available as an elective, and participation is recognised with 3 ECTS credits as “in-depth Language Study” (“Approfondimento Linguistico”) within the framework of “additional activities”, as approved of by the Degree Programme Board, in the same way as the eTandem project (see the first scenario above). The VE project lasts one semester and is offered to students enrolled in the Linguistic and Cultural Mediation degree course. The activities required for the recognition of the VE include participation in an initial meeting with the coordinator, attending the eight weekly 2-hour dialogue sessions, reading the recommended texts, completing a collaborative assignment and writing a weekly reflective journal. The coordinating professor receives weekly updates on student participation and performance in sessions, and a final evaluation. Attendance in all sessions, completion of assignment and reflective diaries and a positive evaluation from Soliya are requirements to obtain the 3 ECTS.

Several students have written their final dissertation on this project, which has had the additional benefit of providing an opportunity for students to carry out empirical research.

At SPGI, the Connect Programme was integrated with additional readings and seminars in order to make it a 6 credit course and was offered, as a stand-alone activity, as an alternative module to the Advanced English Language Course for students enrolled in the European Studies and Human Rights degree courses. Students also had to write an extended essay for their professor in addition to the reflective diaries and collaborative assignment for Soliya.

The constant feedback loop between coordinating professors and Soliya is important to ensure students are participating regularly and are punctual for their sessions. It is also important for the professors to make the course requirements clear to the students and foster a sense of responsibility towards their discussion group, which remains unchanged for the entire 8 weeks of the programme.

— CLIMATE MOVEMENTS

The Sharing Perspectives Foundation (SPF) is a not-for-profit offering contemporary online learning experiences for people to interact constructively across divides, whether national, cultural, social, or political. The SPF model of VE offers engaging content on the specific course thematics; informed by a group process framework, trained facilitators guide the students through meaningful and constructive online dialogues leading to authentic connections and relationships between peers from across the world; and through the interactive and reflective assignments, participants learn how to apply the acquired learning and new skills to their daily practices.

“Climate Movements” is a VE course developed by SPF based on the earlier Interactive Open Online Course (iOOC) “Cultural Encounters”. Thematically, the course focuses on one of the world’s most pressing issues: climate change. Bite-sized video-lectures and other audio-visual materials enable students to develop their views on the topic, and exchange their ideas and perspectives constructively in small groups during online synchronous sessions. During 9 weeks, students from Europe, North Africa and the Middle East have weekly discussions on different aspects of the topic under the guidance of trained facilitators, while completing interactive assignments.

In the Spring 2021 edition of the Climate Movements VE offered by SPF, 104 participants from 6 partner institutions started the VE, with 72 successfully passing the course (meaning that they scored a minimum of 60 out of 100 points, based on the submission of assignments and their attendance to the online group sessions).

During that edition of the Climate Movement course, a partnership between SPF and ESIEE Paris (École Supérieure d’Ingénieurs en Electronique et Electrotechnique de Paris) enabled 23 students to enrol, with 21 successfully finishing it. The course was offered at the ESIEE as an alternative to a regular course on International Communication, enabling students to choose between the regular course or the VE. In autumn 2021 the VE will be offered as an alternative to the physical mobility programme, thus providing an Internationalisation at Home opportunity to less mobile students. At the time of writing this report, the total participation numbers were not yet confirmed. However, the numbers increased with 39 students from ESIEE starting the course and between 300 and 400 participants taking part in the programme overall.

Student participation is monitored by SPF through attendance in the online dialogue sessions as well as completion of the interactive and reflective assignments. In turn, the university reviews the students’ assignments and participation to validate and accredit the VE. The coordinating professor at the ESIEE gives students a grade based on the quality of the written assignments with reference to critical thinking and to the experience of learning in an international classroom. This grade accounted for 50% of the final grade. The other 50% is attributed by SPF.

A number of students from the Climate Movements course expressed clearly that their horizons had been broadened and that they had developed their understanding about climate change, migration and the very different experiences and perspectives people have in different countries. All of the students were happy to have chosen this option.

The main challenge identified was the little contact that took place between the teacher and the students during the VE. While some students were highly autonomous and needed little guidance, other students would have benefitted from contact time with their professor during the term.

— TEACHING AND LEARNING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION IN INTERNATIONAL COMPARISON

This teacher-designed VE course is offered at the University of Erlangen–Nürnberg and the University of Latvia, building upon an existing Erasmus+ Agreement. It is addressed to 2nd and 3rd year students in initial primary teacher education: about 12 students from Germany and 12 students from Latvia take part in it in each iteration. Students at each university enrol following the standard university procedures.

The focus is placed on online collaboration between students, who tackle tasks together from their country-specific perspective. Students work on assignments in an international team and reflect on similarities and differences between the education systems. One of the goals is for students to learn about education systems, teaching, learning and assessment, and to be introduced to intercultural topics such as cultural differences, identity and influences on their world views. Another goal is to enable students to gain experience of working in an international team.

The course lasts 10 weeks and is structured around 5 learning modules: after an introductory “Welcome” (weeks 1 & 2), modules focus on “Education Systems” (weeks 3 & 4), “Teaching and Learning” (weeks 5 & 6), “Assessment” (weeks 7 & 8), and the last two weeks are devoted to a final debrief and reflection.

In terms of requirements, the VE comprises both individual as well as group assignments. Individual tasks mainly consist of learning materials and self-reflection questions. Students work individually on the learning module during the week before the online synchronous sessions. The group assignments are worked on during and after the synchronous sessions. The synchronous sessions take place every second week at a scheduled time on Microsoft Teams. During these sessions, topics related to different cultures are discussed and explored in an active and practical way through a wide range of activities. There are group activities which give students the opportunity to work in small groups. In addition to the introduction and final learning module, the focus in weeks 3+4, 5+6 and 7+8 is on collaboration within transnational groups. There are usually 6 students in each group, working together on one of the topics for 2 weeks and creating a slide presentation for each topic. The groups remain fixed until the final presentation. For every two-week slot, there are two moderators in each group. They are responsible for communication (e.g. contacting other group members, reminding the group to meet the deadlines and contacting the tutors as necessary). However, all group members are responsible for the outcome.

The group moderators change every two weeks and are announced ahead of time. At the end of the course, the two group moderators present the topic of the two-week slot in which they were the moderators.

As far as assessment and accreditation are concerned, a final presentation takes place at the end of the course. Students are also asked to evaluate each other's performance, so they can have some feedback and can practice evaluation through agreed criteria. Students obtain 4 ECTS credits given by their home HEI.

— OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

In their design, the ready-made VE programmes offered by Soliya and SPF have gone through a quality assurance process, and have been externally evaluated and researched over time. During the implementation, great care is taken to ensure student engagement in the online sessions and interactive assignments. Only trained and certified facilitators, supported and monitored by experienced coaches, take part in the online dialogue sessions. Educators from partner HEIs receive weekly updates about students' progress. The assessment of learning outcomes is done by the VE providers as well as the partner HEI. Research has shown that this VE model supports the development of specific skills such as cross-cultural communication, critical thinking, empathy and self-esteem.

Although the ready-made VEs described above are offered as a stand-alone option requiring limited input from the individual professor, it may be advisable to offer support to ensure students understand what is expected of them, and motivation remains high throughout the duration of the course.

One of the advantages of this type of VE is that, as in the case of ESIEE, the course can be offered as an alternative to a physical mobility programme to students who, for a number of reasons, may not be able to travel. This type of solution can be a way to push forward an Internationalisation at Home strategy, as well as internationalising the curriculum, thus offering more inclusive opportunities to develop soft skills and obtain an international experience from home. Or it can encourage students to take part in a short physical mobility exchange after the VE-course, as is the case in the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg VE, where students can go for a short term mobility to the International Students' Research Conference in Riga, which takes place in the following semester. Some German students also decide to spend a whole semester at Riga on an Erasmus+ Exchange.

A major challenge in the recognition and accreditation of ready-made courses may be linked to the perceived difficulty of assigning credits to a course offered by an external organisation.

However, a thorough understanding of the way the programmes are developed, and the possibility of integrating the assessment process by the HEI in charge of accreditation can easily help overcome this challenge, as in the two examples provided in this section. This type of challenge does not occur in the case of a class-to-class VE like the “Teaching and Learning in Primary Education in International Comparison” course, since the VE is entirely developed by internal teaching staff who are able to negotiate accreditation within their own institution.

3.4. VIRTUAL EXCHANGE AS A COMPONENT OF A COURSE (TRADITIONAL OR ONLINE)

A VE offered as a component of a course means that the VE is an integral part of a course and must be carried out in order to successfully complete the course. Recognition and accreditation of the VE component are thus connected to other course requirements. In this way, the VE is used to support the specific learning objectives within that course (as opposed to the previous scenario, where the VE has its own learning objectives and contributes to the wider learning objectives of an entire programme or major). The positioning of the VE is hereby always within a specific course.

The integration of a standard course with a VE component is often motivated by the wish to give the course an international dimension. This can be done by integrating a VE project co-designed by the teachers of the two courses in the partner institutions (as in the Shared Garden and Utrecht), or by including a ‘ready-made’ VE within a single course (see Utrecht, Würzburg, and Limerick).

— SHARED GARDEN

The Shared Garden, based in a physical area situated on the campus in Bordeaux, is a collaborative project between the University of Bordeaux and the University of León, aimed at designing a garden within ecological and sustainable parameters; the students can plant, design their watering system, measure humidity and production. The French students are second year students of Applied Physics and Measurement Engineering, whereas the students in Spain are fourth year students studying Electrical Engineering at the University of León. The specific courses into which the VE was inserted were Fluid Mechanics Engineering in English, which involves 6 ECTS, for the Spanish students, and a Science class in English for the French students following the “international track”. The teachers involved are therefore the Science and English teachers in Bordeaux, and the Fluid Mechanics professor in León.

Because the French participants are second year students, they have less experience in technical solutions, so the Spanish students help them design elements to allow them to save water in their garden.

There have been two iterations of the project, one in the academic year 2018- 2019 and the second one in 2019-2020.

The Shared Garden project was developed mainly to respond to 2 major needs:

- to help students get a better insight into water shortage issues by imagining a cheap eco-friendly watering system, which could be used for our Shared Garden.
- to enable students to improve their communication skills by working in English and to work with an international team; thus, working on their soft skills, such as communication, team work, and problem solving, would be helpful to navigate their future professional life.

The VE is part of a compulsory tutored project for the French students, whereas, for the Spanish students, it is a voluntary component of the PBL (Problem-Based Learning) activity in their Fluid Mechanics course. This means that the VE adds skills to the traditional course, such as problem-solving, intercultural interaction, development of language skills, and working in international environments. These goals have been highly valued by the students from both institutions since they prepare them for their future professional life, as the job market now requires graduates to be flexible, versatile, and open to others.

Due to the different academic calendars at the University of León and the Institute of Technology in Bordeaux, the entire project ran from October to May. First, the French students worked on their own from October to late January. They familiarised themselves with the subject by doing some research on water consumption in general, and by trying to find innovative eco-friendly watering systems. The French students presented their ideas to the Spanish students in February, marking the beginning of the VE. After that, students were divided into small international groups to work on a PBL activity based on a challenge or improvement to the project that they would like to develop together. The teams communicated in English, which is highly relevant in terms of developing their ability to work in an international environment. The teachers acted as guides, integrating knowledge from their different fields. The project was integrated with an activity of co-teaching, where the Spanish professor travelled to Bordeaux to teach for one week. Finally, the Spanish cohort worked on their own from April to May, creating scale models of the irrigation systems and testing them.

The project was very positively evaluated by the students, as it showed them how enriching interdisciplinary projects can be both personally and professionally.

In terms of assessment, the final PBL presentation that the students produced on the application of fluid mechanics concepts accounted for 15% of the global grade (the rest came from the assessment of the entire course), but this mark was the result of the combination of peer assessment, and assessment provided jointly by both teachers. There is no separate recognition or accreditation of the VE component, as these two aspects are given to the entire course within which the VE has been embedded.

— UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, UTRECHT

At the Hogeschool Utrecht University of Applied Sciences (HU), VE is viewed as one way to achieve the university's Internationalisation Strategy, and more specifically Internationalisation at Home, which aims to develop students' intercultural competences without taking part in a physical mobility programme.

At HU there are two types of VE activities: the co-designed, discipline-based VE, and ready-made, intercultural-dialogue-based VE. The former is developed by two teachers from partner universities and focuses around their specific subject matter, and the online exchange provides the international dimension. Students collaborate on tasks related, for instance, to finance and accounting with their peers from other countries.

The intercultural dialogue VE came about through partnerships with VE providers such as Soliya and SPF. This type of VE focuses more on building global perspectives and global competences, which align with the university's internationalisation goals: the online exchange is the core experience, and the content is an instrument to achieve these broader learning goals, such as critical thinking and self-awareness, intercultural understanding, intercultural communication and collaboration.

All VE components at HU are credit-bearing, and are assessed individually against the learning outcomes of the course. VE is regarded as an additional tool to achieve the learning outcomes on a particular module and is thus included in the assessment matrix as one of the learning components. The assessment matrix indicates how VE distinctly adds to the learning outcomes of each course. Moreover, the matrix is accompanied with a reflection report containing questions specifically aligned with VE outcomes. Assessment for VE is considered within the context of each course separately.

The teacher-designed VEs are offered within the Department of Finance and Accounting, the Department of International Business, the Institute for Communication and, to a lesser degree, at the Institute of Languages and the Institute for Education and Teacher Education

The Connect Program, a ready-made VE offered by Soliya, was piloted as a required component in International Communication, and is now integrated in Strategic Management, during the 3rd year of study, which focuses on global strategic issues facing business. The Cultural Encounters VE programmes offered by SPF are Elective courses in the School of Business.

— JULIUS MAXIMILIAN UNIVERSITY (JMU), WÜRZBURG

Students at the JMU in Würzburg can take courses for up to 20 ECTS from the pool of General Key Qualifications subjects. Every faculty or centre at the university, like the Career Centre, can offer courses within this pool, which means that the courses offered in this context can be subject-related or have an interdisciplinary focus. All courses can be attended by all students of the university and they are not limited to specific faculties or programmes. In 2019 the Career Centre decided to use the General Key Qualifications courses to cooperate with partners outside of the university. As a consequence, it decided to include some of the VE activities of the Erasmus+ Virtual Exchange initiative in the General Key Qualifications.

To receive the ECTS credits, students had to successfully complete the VE activities as well as attend two (local) classes at the Career Centre to further strengthen the transversal skill development of the participants.

In support of students' participation in the VEs, the Career Centre offered many advisory services to their students, organised by the regular staff of the Centre, allowing them to collect evidence of the fact that participating students increasingly become aware of the fact that the VE programme enhances not only their foreign language skills in an intercultural and digital setting, but also other transversal skills such as critical thinking and global responsibility on highly topical themes like sustainability, solidarity and climate change. The learning outcomes of the VEs were assessed through a written portfolio in addition to a presentation in class.

When it comes to the challenges and achievements of this experience, the Career Centre has struggled to fit the VE courses in the students' tight schedules. This was not only due to the diversity of disciplines of students within the JMU, but also at their partner institutions. On the other hand, the biggest achievement for JMU's Career Centre programme can be seen in its development of a future-oriented (blended) learning format preparing students for positions of high responsibility in international contexts.

For the JMU, a key factor for long term integration and success of VE remains the availability of external funding. The university has a longstanding and sophisticated intercultural soft-skills programme already developed, which includes digital components. As such, despite the JMU's conviction that the topics and curricula of the VE programmes are an essential integration to what is already offered by the Centre, the university is not investing in VE. Because the percentage of students taking part in the VE was relatively low, it has also been difficult to apply for additional external funding specifically for VE.

— COMMUNICATION ACROSS CULTURES

The Communication across cultures module is one of the elective content specific modules offered at the University of Limerick (UL). The module falls under the internationalisation aim which is at the core of the university strategy, offering students the opportunity to engage in language and intercultural learning while understanding and appreciating their own culture and the culture of others. In recent times it has been shown that students in UL educational context display a lesser degree of interest towards socio-political and global issues in favour of a more localised and regional concern. The VE offered students the unique opportunity to become aware of and engage with such issues while developing their intercultural skills. The module was first designed in 2017 and it was decided to include a VE element in order to provide, together with a theoretical approach, an experiential type of learning. As regards the Virtual Exchange practices, over the years the School of Modern Languages and Applied Linguistics has integrated up to five iOOCs provided by Sharing Perspectives Foundation in various modules. The Cultural Encounters programme was the first to be integrated in the Communication across cultures module presented here.

The Communication across cultures module aims at making students critically aware of the role that language and culture have in intercultural communication. The first part of the module is theoretical and explores views on identity, culture, language and intercultural communication allowing students to reflect on their own identities while critically and emphatically exploring the ones of others. The second part is more practical as students participate in the Cultural Encounters iOOC having the opportunity to put into practice skills of intercultural communicative competence and cultural and intercultural awareness by being in contact with people from different cultural backgrounds in real life contexts. Therefore, the module follows a blended type of approach where traditional face to face lectures are combined with online activities.

The module is twelve weeks long, the face to face part covers the whole length of the course with weekly lectures of two hours and the online delivery is ten weeks long with two hours online mediated sessions per week plus other activities.

During the face to face lectures, students are introduced to topics on interculturality upon which they reflect engaging in critical discussions. The conceptual approach is complemented with the participation in the iOOC online module which is mandatory for students in order for them to receive academic credits.

From a linguistic point of view, a considerable number of UL participants are English native speakers who are sharing perspectives and experiences with English non-native speakers during the VE sessions. Being English the lingua franca, this puts them in the position to reflect upon how to use the language and the messages mediated through it. The rest of the cohort of UL participants are Erasmus and international students who feel that participating in the VE through the medium of the English language provides a valuable opportunity to practice the language itself and discuss socio-political issues.

On an organisational level, before starting the VE, students were introduced to the main features of the iOOC; after an initial registration, they had the possibility to attend a preparatory session that would allow them to get familiar with the platform and tools used throughout the exchanges. It is important to highlight that SPF in conjunction with UL staff provided regular academic and technical support to the participants.

Students had to complete a minimum of 70% of the weekly group-based online seminars and have to actively engage with different tasks such as video lectures, responses to video lectures, video dialogue assignments and a weekly reflective journal. The reflective journal uses a Google form where each student can record their thoughts about the content of the seminars and that of the different discussions and activities undertaken. It is worth noting that the module coordinator and the lectures involved in the module can monitor the attendance and engagement of students in the VE as SPF provides detailed reports on students' participation.

The sessions of online dialogue take place once a week and involve UL students and students from different European and Southern Mediterranean universities. The UL students choose a suitable time for engagement and dedicate two hours per week to the iOOC. These two hours were beside the face to face part of the module, hence technically equipped spaces were provided for students to carry out the online activities. The technical requirements needed to carry out the VE were limited to internet accessibility, a computer (preferably a laptop but mobile phones were used at times too), headphones and a quiet space.

The assessment mechanism of the module is organised in two phases: on one hand there is the assessment provided by SPF on the VE sessions through attendance and participation in the online dialogue sessions, completion of the video lecture response, video dialogue assignments and the weekly reflective journal. All these assessment components count for 60% of the final grade. On the other hand, the assessment of the face to face theoretical lectures consists of a final reflective essay based on the student's experiences in participating in the VE while relating these experiences to the concepts and theories covered during the lectures. These final reflective assignments count for 40% of the students' total grade.

Upon completion of the iOOC, students receive a digital badge in recognition of their multicultural experience after participating in the VE as well as 6 ECTS credits for the module.

During the implementation of the VE, quantitative and qualitative data were gathered respectively through a survey and the final reflective essays. Results from the data reported that, thanks to the participation in the VE, students improved their critical thinking, their soft skills (such as active listening, confidence, respect, empathy, interpretative and reflective skills), their awareness of global issues and broadened their perspectives on cultures and societal matters. The VE fostered sharing, contrasting and exchanging different opinions, perspectives, views and interpretations. Students also agreed that participating in a VE to discuss topics related to Europe and current affairs in general was a very atypical pedagogical approach; however, the experience added a very valuable practical element to their learning, motivating them to get more informed and involved on a societal level. The digital badge received after the successful completion of the VE was considered by the participants as a very positive addition and motivating tool for the whole experience.

— OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

The greatest opportunity of integrating a VE into an existing course might be that it solves the crucial issue of recognition and accreditation: the VE is seen as a component of the entire course, and it does not require additional credits or other forms of recognition. Thus, it is relatively simple to add an international dimension to almost any course offered by a university, through which the students can not only develop their soft skills (such as communicating in a foreign language across diverse cultural settings, also with non-expert audiences) but also get a taste of what the real world (including the world of work) is like.

Another advantage is the possibility of working across disciplines (such as in the Shared Garden example, which combined English, Science and Engineering), enabling students to consider complex problems like climate change and sustainability.

Nevertheless, teachers will need to reflect on whether the VE component is a compulsory or elective part of the course, and the implications of this choice on assessment. Making the VE compulsory or voluntary can affect student motivation and commitment, and might create problems if it is a compulsory part for one cohort and a voluntary part for the students in the partner institution (see again the problem in the Shared Garden example). In addition, if the VE is integrated in an existing course (as opposed to a newly-created one) and the number of credits assigned to the course does not increase, the VE component will need to replace part of the existing content, so that the workload does not increase. For example, with reference to the Limerick case, some issues were highlighted in relation to students' workload and time management having a reported impact on their engagement; as a consequence, some of the face to face time allocated was reduced.

The integration of a teacher-designed VE (as in the Shared Garden example) would seem the better option if teachers wish to tailor the VE to suit their specific disciplinary area, schedules, learning objectives and assessment, and it is relatively easy to design an activity based on a PBL approach. On the other hand, the integration of a ready-made VE can offer the students the possibility to bring their own specific expertise when addressing global issues together with young people living in very different geographical areas, and thus develop crucial skills and understanding to work and live in a global society.

With bilateral VEs, the courses can also be enriched with a short mobility component, if it is possible and suitable, to enable the students to meet each other physically. Again, a PBL approach can foresee a physical mobility component in which the students present the results of their projects to a wider audience. Ready-made VEs, on the other hand, need to be embedded in the wider course, so that the students understand well how the learning objectives of the VE activities contribute to the overall objectives of their course, and do not perceive the former as a disconnected element in their learning process. Notably, as the example of Communication across cultures shows, the integration of an iOOC and VE sessions into a module requires a big support at an institutional level as well as an important commitment by the module coordinator in guiding students in what is perceived as a new pedagogical approach. In any case, the examples provided above show that, even when integrated within an existing course, providing a VE experience for students requires (both human and financial) resources as well as a strategy for recognition and accreditation of the VE component.

CONCLUSIONS

04

— FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

With this report the authors have attempted to illustrate the four main ways in which VE projects can be integrated and accredited at HEI level. These four scenarios have been distilled from a long list of cases of successfully integrated VEs at various institutions across Europe and beyond.

These scenarios intend to illustrate possible ways of integrating VEs as part of broader mobility strategies at HEIs. This means that these strategies or the presented cases are by no means intended as blueprints, but merely as mechanisms to inspire ways of integration and accreditation. Every reality is different, as presented in the various cases where different HEIs integrated and accredited the same VE in different ways. Consequently, scenarios should be approached as illustrations, or inspirations of how integration of VEs could take place within different institutions, which is ultimately always strongly dependent on the local context of an HEI.

Furthermore, the way a VE is accredited may differ between individual students. And this flexibility should be available. To provide an example, let us consider the case of a mobility student at the University of Limerick who follows the Cultural Encounters programme as part of the Communication across cultures course during their time abroad in Ireland. One could argue that for this student, this VE is thus an intertwined component of physical mobility. Or when considering the case of a student taking a VE as a stand alone opportunity but then going on a mobility experience the semester thereafter, it could be argued that the VE has prepared these students for their time abroad. These different experiences, however, do not diminish the intention of the integration and accreditation of the VE as part of a course or as a stand-alone learning activity. As such, this does not change the scenario used to integrate and accredit the mobility experience.

A further argument is that the VE might be born as fitting a specific scenario, yet it might have then evolved to suit more than one scenario. For example, again quoting the Limerick case, the Communication across cultures module has also been offered as an alternative or as preparation to the Erasmus physical mobility, thus providing a pre-mobility activity which makes the VE fits the 1st scenario. In these iterations, students were asked to reflect on how the VE has helped them in getting ready for their time abroad and how their intercultural competence has been impacted by the participation in the VE sessions. In addition to that, increasing attention is currently being paid by Limerick University to offer the course to Erasmus and international students who feel that participating in the VE through the medium of the English language provides a valuable opportunity to practice the language itself and discuss socio-political issues. By offering the VE to mobile students studying at Limerick as part of their physical exchange, the same VE well depicts a case of VE intertwined with the physical mobility (scenario n. 2).

The VE, which was initially developed as a component of a course (scenario n. 4), thus also well fits into the first 2 scenarios hereby depicted. Another example of how a VE can shift among the various scenarios is “Teaching and Learning in Primary Education in International Comparison” (University of Erlangen–Nürnberg, scenario 3): after the VE–course, students can go for a short term mobility to the International Students’ Research Conference in Riga, which takes place in the following semester. Some German students also decide to spend a whole semester at Riga on an Erasmus+ Exchange. Thus, the VE may be also linked to a subsequent short term physical mobility. All these examples make evident that VE projects very frequently have a hybrid nature.

— WAY FORWARD

In this report, four different scenarios for implementing VE within the educational offerings of HEIs have been described, namely 1) as a preparatory or follow-up activity to physical mobility, 2) as an intertwined component during physical mobility, 3) as a stand-alone learning activity and 4) as a component of a course. It has been demonstrated, through the use of examples, the opportunities and challenges linked to each of these four scenarios.

It has also been illustrated how different universities have provided recognition and accreditation of the VE experience. From the examples provided, it is clear that the possibility of obtaining credits for a VE module – whether it is (part of) a core subject or an elective, can affect the motivation of students to take part in the experience. The authors hope that the examples provided in this report of how this can be done can help other HEIs begin the process not only of implementation, but also of accreditation of VE as a valid educational experience for their students.

Looking forward, we would encourage academic staff and administrators to consider other possibilities offered by VE, particularly for internships and placements. This report has shown how VE can offer a more inclusive approach to internationalisation by allowing students who would not take part in a physical mobility programme the opportunity to have an international experience as part of their university studies, and acquire essential transversal skills, such as the ability to work in culturally diverse settings. This objective underlies also the inclusion of international internships and placements, so it would seem that this area would also benefit from VE integration.

Finally, our years of experience in providing training for academic, administrative and technical staff have evidenced a strong interest in the opportunities for staff development and/or exchange (both blended or stand-alone) offered by VE. This is undoubtedly another area worth considering by universities aspiring to become truly international institutions. To this end, it would be worth considering the implementation of VE projects as part of Continuous Professional Development. For example, a VE could be set up among various HEIs, such as those which are part of a network or which are partnering in projects or similar initiatives, whereby their staff are trained on how to deal with intercultural issues in their everyday work.

